

VARIOUS TYPES OF ASSESSMENT IN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING

Nematova Zebo Tursunboevna

Bukhara State Medical Institute, Bukhara.
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ABSTRACT

This article will first explain the diagnostic assessment's meaning, list the types of diagnostic assessment, along with relevant diagnostic assessment examples. Then it will illustrate the importance of diagnostic assessment in education. We will also cover the advantages and disadvantages of diagnostic assessment in education.

Quality control is of utmost importance in every industry and sphere of life. Assessments are a useful way of maintaining quality. In the education field, the assessment process utilizes empirical data on student learning to make the learning process more effective and enhance student development. Assessment is the process of collecting useful and relevant data and information from various sources to develop insights into students' understanding, knowledge, and takeaways from the educational experience.

There are various types of assessments available to assess progress and skill levels for this purpose. These are:

Diagnostic Assessment: The purpose of diagnostic assessment is to gauge students' knowledge, skills, strength, and weaknesses beforehand.

Formative Assessment: This is used to collect information on students' understanding throughout the learning process to help teachers adjust their strategies accordingly.

Summative Assessment: This is used to measure students' knowledge after a subject has been taught.

Ipsative Assessment: It is used to track students' performance by comparing their current scores with their past scores.

Norm-referenced Assessment: It is used to compare and rank a group of students.

Criterion-referenced Assessment: It is used to compare a student's score to a set learning standard or performance level.

This article will first explain the diagnostic assessment's meaning, list the types of diagnostic assessment, along with relevant diagnostic assessment examples. Then it will illustrate

the importance of diagnostic assessment in education. We will also cover the advantages and disadvantages of diagnostic assessment in education.

The purpose of diagnostic assessments is to help identify problems with a certain instruction style and provide insights into improvement that can be done in the quality of delivery. Diagnostic assessments in education help educators understand their students' strengths, weaknesses, knowledge level, and skillset prior to beginning instruction. Diagnostic assessment examples include pre-assessment tests that give you a snapshot of or diagnose knowledge to screen students.

For instance, if a teacher wants to start a lesson on two-digit multiplication with young pupils, they can use diagnostic assessment to make sure the lesson is delivered well. They will want to understand if the students have grasped fact families, number place values, and one-digit multiplication before moving on to more complicated questions.

Diagnostic assessments collect data on what the students already know about a specific subject or topic.

These diagnostic assessment examples will make the diagnostic assessment meaning clearer. The following are ways in which instructors from different fields use various types of diagnostic assessment tools:

Introductory physics: A set of conceptual questions is used to assess understanding of physics fundamentals at the start of the course.

Psychology: The instructor conducts a survey to understand students' assumptions about concepts such as the

nature of mind versus the nature of behavior.

Course with group work: The instructor rolls out a self-assessment, where group members rate themselves on certain parameters. Specific examples of their previous group work are collected to understand each individual's mindset.

Creative or fine arts: The instructor collects portfolios to judge the artistic abilities of fine arts students.

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Assessments come in many shapes and sizes. For those who are new to assessment or just starting out, the terms can be hard to sort out or simply unfamiliar. Knowing one type of assessment from another can be a helpful way to understand how best to

use assessment to your advantage. That's why we've taken the time to layout the different types of assessment for you in this post.

The multi-faceted nature of assessments means that educators can leverage them in a number of ways to provide valuable formal or informal structure to the learning process. The main thing to remember is that the assessment is a learning tool. What all assessments have in common is that they provide a snapshot of student understanding at a particular time in the learning process.

Reasonably so, when you were a student yourself, you may not have been aware of the variety of assessments that teachers leverage. To the average student, or anyone who has ever been a student, the word 'test' has a pretty clear cut definition and it usually includes some level of anxiety and expectation about a final outcome. But, to educators, tests – or assessments – are actually quite multi-faceted and have both formal and informal places throughout the learning process.

Assessments can run the gamut from start to finish when it comes to instruction. Think of it like a long distance race that has a start and finish line and many stations to refuel in between. The race can be any instructional period of time, such as a unit, a quarter, or even the full year. In this metaphor, the student is the runner and the teacher is the coach who is trying to help the student run the race as well as they possibly can. Different assessments types, when utilized by the coach (teacher) in the right way, can help the runner (student) run the race better and more effectively.

Here are some more types of diagnostic assessments that can be used for

assessing students: Journals, quiz/test, conference/interview, posters, performance tasks, mind maps, gap-closing, student surveys, anticipation guides.

There are various advantages of different types of diagnostic assessment in education that help achieve the purpose of diagnostic assessment, which is to improve quality. These are:

They provide insights to educators to create customized instructions.

They are usually informal and easy to use.

They don't require high-level training and don't have standardized protocols to follow.

Teachers can further refine or change their methods at any time. For instance, a teacher can start with easier diagnostic assessment examples and then move on to journals or audits.

Such assessments show quick results once you're used to them.

Instructors can easily share their learnings with their peers.

The drawbacks of diagnostic assessment could be:

They don't take into consideration anything that needs to be done post the delivery of a lesson.

The importance of diagnostic assessments also diminishes in large groups.

A teacher may develop inaccurate assumptions about the student's knowledge of a subject and overlook that particular topic during the unit.

Students new to this kit can become anxious.

Generally, for this assessment to be administered correctly and executed reliably, special training may be required.

Plus, this whole process is quite time-consuming.

In summary, the diagnostic assessment serves to know the situation of the students, exactly what is needed to increase their knowledge, and first of all provides very useful information that will

help the teachers to better plan their lessons. Obviously, this is a necessary tool that needs to be done from time to time to know what decisions are best to make in this way students could choose the right path for their education.

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